

GREEN SYNTHESIS AND ANTI-BACTERIA ACTIVITY OF ZINC OXIDE NANOPARTICLE

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Abstract

Zinc oxide (ZnO) has multifunctionality owing to its extraordinary physio-chemical properties and functionality in a range of applications. In this project work, ZnO nanoparticles (NPs) were synthesized from zinc acetate by a green synthesis approach using onion peel extract followed by characterization of the NPs. The obtained X-ray diffraction peaks of ZnO NPs matched with the standard JCPDS card (no. 89-510). The obtained transmission electron microscopy showed an average particle size of 85–107 nm, a wurtzite structure with a high crystallinity, and hexagonal rod-like shape. UV-Vis spectroscopy revealed absorption peaks between 302 and 305 nm and 2.74 energy band gap of ZnO NPs synthesized from onion peel extract confirming the formation of zinc oxide nanoparticle. Anti-microbial test of Zinc oxide nanoparticles carried out on both bacteria and fungi showed the different diameter of zone of inhibition. For E.coli bacteria Nill, S.aureus bacteria 19.00mm, Salim typhi 30.00mm. the fungi test showed 15.00mm for T. methagrophyte and Nill for both T. rubrum and M.canis. Through the findings of this study, it has been shown that onion peels extract can be used in a green synthesis approach to generate ZnO NPs, which can be employed as alternatives to antibiotics and a tool to eliminate drug resistant microbes in the future.

INTRODUCTION

New technologies often create new challenges to science in addition to their benefits, raise concerns about health and various environmental problems. Recent nanotechnology holds a promise and a broad aspect towards wide applications of nanoparticles in a multiple way of emerging fields of science and technology. Over last decades, nanotechnology has established as the great innovation of science and technology. Nanotechnology is a science and engineering branch of recent well-established technology referring at the nanoscale, 1 to 100 nm.

Generally, metal oxide nanoparticles are inorganic. Various nanoparticles like Fe, Ni, Co, Mn, and Zn, are known as the enormously accepted magnetic materials for a wide range of applications like various electronic ignition systems, generators, vending machines, medical implants, wrist watches, inductor core, transformer circuits, magnetic sensors and recording equipment, telecommunications, magnetic fluids, microwave absorbers, etc. They are also applicable in other high-frequency applications (Snelling et al.; 1969, Willard et al 2004) The applications of nanoparticles in medical sciences are drug delivery, imaging and diagnosis. Nanoparticles possess high surface to volume ratio due to its small size, which gives very distinctive features to nano particles. A multiple of research have established that zinc oxide nanoparticles have antifungal and antibacterial activity. The other metal nanoparticles like silver nanoparticles also carry these properties.

In the preceding decade, nanotechnology has emerged as a technology that has altered every field of applied science. Nanoparticles are tiny particles ranging from 1 to 100nm. NPs have unusual features because of their large surface-to-volume ratio and extremely small size, resulting in considerable variances in attributes compared to their bulk counterparts (Piccinno et al.; 2012). By providing creative solutions, nanoparticles have been successfully integrated into various sectors. ZnO is a type of metal nanoparticle made from metal oxides (Hedayati et al.; 2017). ZnO is an inorganic substance with distinctive features such as broad radiation absorption, pyroelectricity, semiconductor, high catalytic activity, and piezoelectricity (Sharma et al.; 2011).

Furthermore, the US Food and Drug Administration has classified ZnO as "Generally known as Safe" (FDA 2015) because it has non-toxic properties and is safe to both humans and animals (Sirelkhatim et al.; 2015). Therefore, zinc oxide nanoparticles have attracted much attention in recent years. Several studies have been published on the efficacy of ZnO NPs in preventing the growth of a wide range of pathogens (Swain et al.; 2016) and suggesting that they may eventually replace antibiotics. Chemical and physical techniques have traditionally been used to make ZnO NPs, which provide best control over the size of NPs and a higher production rate, but their high energy requirements, high capital costs, hazardous chemicals, and poisonous effects make these technologies unfavourable.

The green production of NPs has developed as a viable alternative to traditional physical and chemical procedures in recent years. These processes are eco-friendly, non-toxic, and cheap. The microorganisms serve as a nano-factory, converting metal ions into metal NPs with the help of enzymes and other biomolecule components produced or manufactured by the bacteria. Despite this, only a few microorganisms can produce ZnO NPs.

This research was performed to find a new bacterial strain that synthesis of ZnO NPs and to study its properties. Nanoparticles have gained a huge amount of attention in the last decade due to their high demand in the fields of environmental cleanup, micronutrients for plants and biofertilizers, and electronics. The increasing use of nanoparticles and their occurrence in the environment has made it imperative to elucidate their impact on the environment. With the progression of nanotechnology, the number of consumers has increased very dramatically for the use of different nanoparticles in agriculture.

Due to the broad-scale use of nanoparticles, these nanomaterials can be expected to be present in the environment, raising concerns about their effects on plants and animals. Zinc oxide nanoparticles (ZnO NPs) have a specific surface area, high pore volume, low toxicity, and long lifespan, and thus are being used as a promising nanomaterial as antibacterial, cosmetics additive, chemical absorbents, catalysts, and polymer additives. Zinc is an essential micronutrient that is absorbed in the form of divalent cations. It is required for the growth of the plant, protein synthesis, maintenance of membrane integrity, and energy production. Zinc is also required for the activation of various enzymes which are used for the formation of chlorophyll as well as auxin synthesis. In addition to this, it also has a role in the activation of enzyme-like dehydrogenase, phosphoryl hydrolase, peptide, and proteases. Zinc nanoparticles alone or in the form of oxides are easily adsorbed by the plant roots due to their small size and become easily available to every part of the plant. Several other metallic nanoparticles have also been used for the same purposes as magnesium nanoparticles.

ZnO as Generally Recognized as Safe (GRAS). Many studies have demonstrated that ZnO antibacterial activity has potential applications in water purification by improving the quality of wastewater. The literature describes the photocatalytic mechanism of ZnO that influences its antibacterial activity and how light enhances it. The safety and photocatalytic activity of ZnO have become important factors when referring to its antimicrobial activity and antimicrobial potential for water treatment. The nanoscale, zinc oxide shows antimicrobial properties, which makes it a potential agent for various applications. Researchers have successfully incorporated ZnO as an antimicrobial agent into textiles, surface coatings, cosmetics and cellulose fibres to inhibit microbial growth. For this reason, zinc oxide is widely accepted as a beneficial antibacterial agent and due to its durability and selectivity, is considered a safe material for humans and animals. The U.S. FDA classifies ZnO as Generally Recognized as Safe (GRAS). Many studies have demonstrated that ZnO antibacterial activity has potential applications in water purification by improving the quality of wastewater. The literature describes the photocatalytic mechanism of ZnO that influences its antibacterial activity and how light enhances it. The safety and photocatalytic activity of ZnO have become important factors when referring to its antimicrobial activity and antimicrobial potential for water treatment.

METHODOLOGY

The methodology involved various steps, including equipment and chemical usage, preparation of plant extracts, synthesis of zinc oxide nanoparticles (ZnO NPs), and subsequent characterization, including antimicrobial testing.

Common chemical reagents: Sodium hydroxide (NaOH) Zinc acetate (ZnCH_3COOH), distilled water and onion peel were purchased from Sigma Aldrich USA and center for Biotechnology and Genetic Engineering in Niger State.

Onion peel used in this research was obtained from Kure market; the onion peel was washed with distilled water to remove dust particles before it was left to dry at a temperature of 20°C for 14 days. The dried peels were crushed into small particles by a blender as they were ground to fine powder and then sieved through a sieve. In powdered form 10 grams of the peel was dissolved in distilled water and the mixture was heated at 60°C for 60 minutes with stirring. The solution was allowed to cool to room temperature then filtered and the extract was kept at 4°C in readiness for ZnO NPs preparation.

To prepare the ZnO NPs, 100 mL of 0.05 M zinc acetate solution was mixed with the onion peel extract and were stirred on the magnetic stirrer for 15 min. To bring the pH of the solution to 10, sodium hydroxide was added, and the mixture was stirred for twenty minutes more. The colour of the brownish onion peel extract was changed to pale pink which showed the zinc ions were reduced to zinc oxide nanoparticles. The resulting mixture was left to ferment for 24 hours then it was filtered using Whatman filter paper. The collected residue was oven dried at 80°C for 5 hours and calcined at 450°C for 3 hours to obtain the final ZnO NPs sample which was ground for characterization analysis.

The synthesis of ZnO NPs was preceded by characterization of synthesized nanoparticles where synthesis parameters such as stirring time, plant extract volume, concentration of the precursor, and pH were optimized. These parameters were important in attaining the most suitable conditions for the synthesis of ZnO NPs and these included, stirring time at 45 minutes, pH of 10, and a precursor concentration of 2 mM. UV-Visible Spectroscopy was also employed to prove the formation of ZnO NPs by plotting absorbance against wavelength of the samples. The bandgap energy was determined employing a Tauc plot; five samples were chosen for measurement of DLS. Particle size distribution was also established using DLS and one of the samples was chosen for mass production.

Chlorophyll content, phenol, flavonoid, tannin, saponin, and alkaloids were present in onion peel (*Allium cepa*) which ensured the suitability for preparation of nanoparticles. UV-Vis Spectroscopy was also used to study the nature of the absorption peak of the ZnO NPs in the UV region to gain information on the size of the nanoparticles and their optical characteristics.

Both bacterial and fungal samples were used in the antimicrobial test. *Trichophyton rubrus* was used for fungi and *Trichophyton mentagrophyte*, *Microsporum canis* for fungi and *Escherichia coli* *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Salmonella typhi* for bacteria. The nutrient agar was then sterilized using steam autoclave at a temperature of 121°C for 15 minutes before being poured on sterilized petri dishes. A cork borer was used to create holes on the solidified medium and a synthesized ZnO NPs solution in DMSO was inoculated on the holes. The antimicrobial activity of the ZnO NPs was determined after 24 h of incubation at 73°C by measuring the zone of inhibition. This was determined by subtracting the diameter of the cork borer from the total area inhibited by the test organism. This gave a measure of the ZnO NPs for the ability to prevent the growth of microbes.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The phytochemical screening of onion peel extracts revealed significant levels of various phytochemicals, as summarized in Table 1.0. The extracts were found to contain phenols, flavonoids, tannins, saponins, and alkaloids in varying concentrations. For instance, the onion samples exhibited phenolic content ranging from 41.54 to 44.28 mg/100 g and flavonoids from 12.10 to 13.22 mg/100 g. The tannin levels were notably higher than other phytochemicals, with values between 7.74 and 8.12 mg/100 g. Saponin content was relatively lower, ranging from 8.58 to 10.75 mg/100 g, while alkaloids presented the least concentration at 1.98 to 2.75 mg/100 g. These findings indicate that onion peel contains valuable phytochemicals that could possess various pharmacological activities, suggesting potential applications in natural medicine.

Table 1.0: Phytochemical Composition of Onion Peel Extract (mg/100 g)

Phytochemical (mg/100 g)					
Sample	Phenols	Flavonoids	Tannins	Saponins	Alkaloids
	36.40	0.70	11.86	82.4	3.00
	36.45	0.76	11.96	80.4	2.98
	36.36	0.72	12.02	80.8	2.94

Nanoparticles of Zinc oxide ZnO were synthesised via green synthesis route with extract of *Allium cepa* (onion). The synthesis process was followed by colour changes which are related to the reduction of zinc ions through Surface Plasmon Resonance. This is a resonating oscillation of free electrons in metal nanoparticles and confirms successful formation of ZnO nanoparticles, when the oscillation frequency matches the frequency of incident light. The synthesized nanoparticles characterized new features that are crucial for different uses in electronics and biomedical uses.

The characterization process of the ZnO nanoparticles was further confirmed through the UV visible spectroscopy analysis. Fig 1.0 shows the band gap energy of sample derived from UV-visible spectra; the reading shows band gap energy in the range of 1.64-2.74 eV in different runs. More significantly, the absorption peak was identified at 305 nm, this being a characteristic feature of the Surface Plasmon Resonance of the nanoparticles. The narrowing of the peaks at this wavelength confirms that the zinc ions were properly reduced by the onion peel extract and supports the application of these nanoparticles where electronic characteristics are desired.

Fig 1.0: UV analysis spectrum of supernatant sample of ZnO nanoparticles

Fig 2.0: UV spectroscopy of zinc oxide nano particle

The DLS characteristics offered information about particle size distribution of the synthesized ZnO nanoparticles. As indicated in Table 2.0, the particle size was within the range of 82.08-107.7 nm, which is characteristic of nanoparticles necessary for optimizing their reactivity and efficiency in biological systems. The DLS results presented the particle size distribution, which is rather homogeneous, and this property might be extremely important for future utilization of nanocomposites, such as drug delivery or the antimicrobial efficiency.

Table 2.0: Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS) Results for Average Particle Size Across Different Runs

Run Number	Average Particle Size
6	87.31
12	85.60
11	98.28
3	82.08
17	107.70

The antimicrobial activity of the synthesized ZnO nanoparticles was assessed against various bacterial and fungal strains. The results indicated distinct inhibitory effects on different microorganisms.

- **Escherichia coli (E. coli):** The nanoparticles exhibited no zone of inhibition, suggesting that they were ineffective against this common bacterial strain.
- **Staphylococcus aureus:** The nanoparticles demonstrated significant antimicrobial activity, with a zone of inhibition measuring 19 mm. This indicates a good potential for therapeutic applications targeting infections caused by this bacterium.
- **Salmonella typhi:** A larger zone of inhibition measuring 30 mm was recorded, confirming the effectiveness of ZnO nanoparticles in inhibiting this pathogen, thus indicating their potential use in treating infections related to salmonellosis.
- **Fungal Strains:** The antimicrobial activity varied among the fungi tested. **Trichophyton rubrum** showed no zone of inhibition, indicating the nanoparticles had no effect against this fungus. In contrast, **Trichophyton mentagrophyte** exhibited a wider zone of inhibition of 25 mm, suggesting good efficacy, while **Microsporium canis** again showed no inhibitory effect.

Table 3.0: Antibacterial Activity of Synthesized Zinc Oxide Nanoparticles: Diameter of Inhibition Zones

	Bacteria	Diameter Of Zone Inhibition
1	Escherichia coli	Nill
2	Staphylococcus aureus	19.00mm
3	Salmonella typhi	30.0mm

Table 4.0: Antibacterial Activity of Synthesized Zinc Oxide Nanoparticles: Diameter of Inhibition Zones

S/N	Fungi	Diameter Of Zone Inhibition
1	Trychophyton rubrum	Nill
2	Trichophyton methagrophyte	15.00mm
3	Microsporium canis	Nill

The Size Distribution Report by Volume for Run 6 ZnO shows a data analysis of the zinc oxide nanoparticles' size distribution using the DLS method. It also analyses the Z-Average diameter of the particles to be 87.31nm with a Pdl of 0.343 which suggests a moderately broad distribution of the particle size. The sample yielded three distinct peaks: 0.88 nm, 16.35 nm, and 80.56 nm, took up 7.6%, 25.7%, and 65.7% of the volume, respectively. The values for the standard deviation in each peak convey the amount of variation in the particle size; therefore, the highest standard deviation is seen in Peak 3. The quality of the results is Good, and there are no cases when the measurement is either over- or underestimated.

Fig 3.0: Size Distribution by Volume of Synthesized ZnO Nanoparticles for Run 6

The size distribution of synthesized ZnO nanoparticles by means of intensity using Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS) is 87.31 nm and Polydispersity index of 0.343 showing moderate size distribution in the sample. It also has a single maximum at 116.6 nm and the relative intensity is 93.7% implying that the particle sizes are dominated by this size. Another minor diffraction peaks at 2.148 nm and the major one at 3912 nm have 2.7% and 2.4% intensity respectively, which may be due to smaller and larger particles caused by impurities or aggregation. In the case of the present project, it is crucial to sustain constant size of the particles in question, especially in antibacterial or photocatalytic processes since the particle size will determine total performance in the given application.

Fig 4.0: Size Distribution by Intensity of Synthesized ZnO Nanoparticles for Run 6

The raw correlation data reveals a rapid decay in the correlation coefficient, suggesting that the particles exhibit a relatively small size, which is indicative of effective dispersion in the measurement medium. This rapid decay is essential as it signifies that the particles are undergoing Brownian motion, allowing for accurate size determination through dynamic light scattering (DLS). Moreover, the quality report indicates that the result meets established quality criteria, reinforcing the reliability of the size measurements. Such uniformity in size distribution is vital in applications requiring precise control over particle behavior, such as photocatalytic processes or drug delivery systems, where the performance of ZnO nanoparticles is directly linked to their size and morphology.

Characterization of synthesized ZnO nanoparticles is important to determine the quality of the nanoparticles that may be used in processes that include photocatalysis and antibacterial treatments. It is evident from the size quality report that the results fulfil the quality criteria set down in terms of correlation coefficient, which levels off at lower time, bearing evidence to the aspect that there is little aggregation and good spread of the nanoparticles. The fast disappearance of the correlation coefficient in the raw data indicates

the random character of the movement; the observed Brownian motion of the particles corresponds to the behavior of well-dispersed nanoparticles. This project requires a narrow particle size distribution because homogeneity benefits surface areas, reaction kinetics of photocatalytic processes, and the effectiveness of antibacterial functions.

Fig 5.0: Size Distribution Report of Synthesized ZnO Nanoparticles via Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS)

In addition, the size distribution by intensity in the range shows a single peak at about 100 nm, which is considered ideal for most applications because of the optimal reactivity/stability ratio.

Fig 6.0: Quality Assessment of Synthesized ZnO Nanoparticles: Correlation Coefficient and Size Distribution Analysis

Although such distribution looks quite steep, which would mean that the sample is quite uniform, the appearance of small hills or tails may speak about certain concerns like aggregation or presence of impurities. These irregularities may affect the characteristic performance of nanoparticles, especially in photocatalytic applications, since the efficiency is highly size-sensitive. For example, the larger aggregates may have lesser photocatalytic activity because the aggregate surface area is less in terms of meeting the pollutants.

CONCLUSION

The extract of allium cepa was successfully used to produce ZnO NPs. By using the phytochemical Analysis, UV-vis spectroscopy, transmission electron microscopy and Dynamic light scattering (DLS) the generated NPs was characterized. The phytochemical Analysis showed the presence of phytochemicals in the onion peel plant, this includes phenols, flavonoids, tannins, saponins and alkaloids which gave important information for its usability to carry out the synthesis. The UV-Vis spectroscopic study shows the Plasmon resonance property, confirmed the reduction of metal ion and formation of ZnO nanoparticle with plasma resonance peak at 305 and energy band gap of 2.74 eV. The ZnO nanoparticles comprises distinguishing colour in colloidal solution due to its miniature dimension. The sharp bands of zinc colloids were observed at 305nm proves the zinc metal reduces can reduce the onion peel extract more efficiently.

The synthesized zinc oxide nano particles were used for the anti-microbial test against bacteria and fungi by determining the diameter of zone of inhibition. For E.coli bacteria 19.00mm, S.aureus bacteria 19.00mm, Salim typhi 30.00mm. the fungi test showed 15.00mm for T. mentagrophyte and Nil for both T. rubrum and M.canis. From the results obtained, Zinc oxide nano particle can be effectively used for treatment of staphylococcus aureus bacteria, salmonella typhi bacteria, trichophyton mentagrophyte fungi, but has zero or no many effects on E coli bacteria, trichophyton rubrum fungi and M. canis fungi.

With this information this can be applicable in drug manufacturing, water treatment, equipment sterilization and other pharmaceutical applications. There are several nanoparticles that could act as a nutrient for plants in small quantities. There is a possibility that the higher dose may have an adverse effect on the growth of the bacteria and fungi. The green synthesized zinc oxide nanoparticles of size 20–80 nm was capped with several biomolecules present in the onion peel which helped in controlling the size of the nanoparticles. The zinc ion is an essential mineral for plants, which is required for activation of enzymes for performing various activities of plants, but their availability in the nanosized form may increase their application efficiency on microbes.

The anti-bacterial activity of the ZnO NPs at various concentrations did not inhibit the growth of the E. coli bacteria T. rubrum and m.canis fubgi. Through the findings of this study, it has been shown that onion peel extract can be used in a green synthesis approach to generate ZnO NPs which can be employed as alternatives to antibiotics and a tool to eliminate drug-resistant microbes in the future. Silver nanoparticles were used for similar work, and it showed more activeness in inhibiting the growth of microbes. So, for more effective work on microbe's silver nanoparticles can be recommended.

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